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Storytelling

Reviewed by **Martina Vasil**

Engaging Musical Practices – A Sourcebook for Elementary General Music

Edited by Suzanne L. Burton and Alison M. Reynolds
National Association for Music Education, 2018

A sourcebook is a small collection of writings, usually on a specific subject, that, by definition, provides a resource for others for future writing, study, or research. *Engaging Musical Practices – A Sourcebook for Elementary General Music* serves that exact purpose. Within its pages, editors Suzanne L. Burton and Alison M. Reynolds bring together 15 authors to share their expertise on a variety of topics relevant for the elementary general music classroom. Research for each topic is succinctly summarized in every chapter, and then a variety of practical suggestions, lesson ideas, and activities are described in detail.

Elizabeth Cassidy Parker begins with her chapter on the importance of general music for children’s education. She posits central values of a general music education: (1) active musical experiences centered on process, not product, (2) strong relationships with students, (3) an ethic of care, and (4) the self. In the next five chapters (2 through 6), authors describe the related research and offer practical applications for using active music making skills in the elementary general music classroom. Kimberly Inks writes about active listening, Joanne Rutkowski about singing, Wendy H. Valerio about movement, Karen Howard about folk dancing, and Julie Scott about instrument playing.

Chapters 7 and 8 offer more theoretical understandings on teaching improvisation and composition and teaching music literacy. Heather Nelson Shouldice provides many suggestions for scaffolding improvisation and composition in the classroom and provides useful lesson ideas. Suzanne L. Burton emphasizes the importance of sound over symbol and suggests a progression for teachers to follow when guiding children toward the use of traditional music notation.

The remaining chapters (9 through 15) serve as resources on a variety of topics important to cultivating a successful elementary general music classroom. Kerry B. Rezone explains when and how to use technology in the classroom, Lisa Lehmborg gives recommendations for using non-Western music in the classroom (“world” music), and Cynthia M. Colwell notes the relevant research and provides practical suggestions for teaching students with special needs (touching upon music therapy). Sandra Nicolucci details the National Core Arts Standards and how they can be applied, Cynthia Crump Taggart describes many ideas for using assessment in the classroom, and Katie Wolf Martinenza offers strategies for a student-centered approach to classroom management. To conclude, Ann Marie

Stanley reviews the many different ways teachers can engage in professional development and presents recommendations specifically to help the kindergarten through Grade 5 general music teacher.

This sourcebook can be read back-to-back, as I did, but it may be more beneficial to use it to address specific challenges or questions a teacher might have in the classroom or topical areas that preservice music teachers want to learn more about. I earmarked several chapters that will be useful as supplemental readings for my elementary methods class and also marked activities to try in my own general music classroom. A suggestion for the editors would be to consider adding online supplemental material for the book. At times I thought watching a video of a recommended activity, rather than reading through it, would be more

effective, especially for those new to teaching who might find it difficult to conceptualize activities they have never seen or experienced. Nevertheless, I found this book very informative and recommend it for a wide array of readers—the kindergarten through Grade 5 general music teacher, preservice music teachers, and music teacher educators. ■

MARTINA VASIL, PhD, is assistant professor of music education and division coordinator—department of music education and music therapy at the University of Kentucky (UK). She teaches collegiate courses in general music, popular music education, and qualitative research and directs the summer Orff Schulwerk Teacher Education program at UK. Martina continues to teach music to children pre-K through Grade 6 parttime at Lexington Montessori School. She has completed three levels of Orff Schulwerk Teacher Education and currently serves on *The Orff Echo* editorial board.

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